

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for **African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.**

D2.2 Online database with DIHs Capacity Building programmes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101016687.

Document details	
Project Acronym/ Name:	AfriConEU
Project URL:	www.africoneu.eu
Project Type:	Innovation Action (IA)
EU CALL:	H2020-ICT-2018-20 (Information and Communication Technologies)
Grant Agreement No.:	101016687
Project Start Date:	February 2021
Project End Date:	January 2024
Workpackage:	WP2 Context and state of the art analysis
Deliverable:	D2.2 Explore existing capacity building programmes for DIHs and build upon existing good practices, experiences and lessons learned
Due date of Deliverable:	31/08/21
Actual Submission Date:	31/08/21
Name of Lead Beneficiary for this deliverable:	Report Author: Sasa Straus (INOVACIJSKO TEHNOLOSKI GROZD MURSKA SOBOTA – ITC)
Reviewed by:	Adam Cecchini, Joseph Gaylord (dpixel) Ana Aleixo, Margarida Vieira, Marta Coto (INOVA+)
Revision:	5.0
Dissemination Level:	Public

Document History			
Version	Date	Comment	Modifications made by
1.0	13.08.2021	First draft of the document	Sasa Straus (ITC)
2.0	20.08.2021	Revision of the document and inputs to draft	Adam Cecchini, Joseph Gaylord (dpixel)
3.0	25.08.2021	Second version of completed report	Sasa Straus (ITC)
4.0	30.08.2021	Final Revision	Ana Aleixo, Margarida Vieira, Marta Coto (INOVA+)
5.0	31.08.2021	Final version	Sasa Straus (ITC)

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© Partners of the AfriConEU Consortium, 2021
 This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Acknowledgements

We extend our gratitude to the members of the AfriConEU consortium and especially dpixel for reviewing the document.

Glossary and Abbreviations	
AFRICONEU	The first Trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European DIHs
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	8
PROJECT SUMMARY	9
INTRODUCTION	10
APPROACH AND METHODOLOGY	12
Overview of DIH ecosystem = DIH helpers	12
Overview of Capacity Building Programmes for DIHS, both fully operational and those in preparation	40
CONCLUSION.....	56

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Task of DIHS as defined by the European Commission.....	10
---	----

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: DIH services	12
Table 2: Basic information about DIH Networks.....	13
Table 3: Basic information about DIH HELP	14
Table 4: Basic information about Smart Agri Hubs.....	15
Table 5: Basic information about AI DIH network	16
Table 6: Basic information about ICT Innovation for Manufacturing SMEs	17
Table 7: Basic information about The Smart Anything Everywhere.....	18
Table 8: Basic information about DigiFed.....	19
Table 9: Basic information about HUBCAP	20
Table 10: Basic information about Digital for Development (D4D) Hub.....	21
Table 11: Basic information about ITU-D Digital Innovation Ecosystems.....	22
Table 12: Basic information about EIT Digital.....	23
Table 13: Basic information about AfriLabs.....	24
Table 14: Basic information about Boosting digital innovation.....	25
Table 15: Basic information about DIH-World.....	26
Table 16: Basic information about Open Data Incubator Europe.....	27
Table 17: Basic information about European Network for Pilot Production Facilities and Innovation Hubs	28
Table 18: Basic information about European cluster collaboration platform	29
Table 19: Basic information about The European Resource Efficiency Knowledge Centre.....	30
Table 20: Basic information about The Africa-Europe Innovation Partnership.....	31
Table 21: Basic information about Ghana Hubs Network	32
Table 22: Basic information about Innovation Support Network - Hubs	33
Table 23: Basic information about The Association of Startup and SMEs Enablers of Kenya	34
Table 24: Basic information about Funding Box	35
Table 25: Basic information about I4Trust.....	36

Table 26: Basic information about Impact Ed Tech	37
Table 27: Basic information about The European Coordination Hub for Open Robotics Development	38
Table 28: Basic information about Smart Factories in new EU Member States.....	39
Table 29: List of capacity building programmes for DIHs	41

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH) are support organisations that make businesses more competitive by speeding up the development and uptake of digital innovations. DIHs are one-stop shops that help companies become more competitive concerning their business/production processes, products, or services using digital technologies.

The selection of materials was based on the identified needs in the AfriConEU community and whether, following our guiding principles, an open-access webinar or template is available on the topics. Multiple projects addressed some topics. The decision on which training to include in the AfriConEU portal has been based on the team's judgment and the relevance of the training.

This overview is actually a snapshot of a live document that will continuously be updated by the team as new needs in the community are identified and new trainings emerge.

The mapped materials will support new DIHs in setting up their organisation and already operating DIHs in optimising their operations and services. Some of the trainings identified are of importance in both of these stages.

Existing organisations/initiatives/networks/projects as DIH helpers for strengthening DIHs capacities in Africa and Europe are also presented, as they can offer DIHs help on various topics.

PROJECT SUMMARY

The AfriConEU project aims to strengthen and reinforce the digital innovation ecosystems in Africa by targeting existing Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and supporting them through capacity building and networking activities. African DIHs are playing a central role in the development of digital entrepreneurship. By raising their capacities to tackle the challenges they face, they will be more effective in driving digital innovation forward.

The AfriConEU project will connect DIHs from Nigeria, Uganda, Ghana and Tanzania with DIHs from Europe with the aim to:

- Facilitate knowledge and experience sharing;
- Drive the development of mutually beneficial partnerships;
- Support the creation of collective projects to boost the digital economy, empower youth, and foster innovation and growth.

The project will develop, test, and validate the "AfriConEU Networking Academy," an innovative mechanism for connecting and sharing best practices, experiences, and resources among DIHs in Africa and between DIHs in Africa and EU, in a comprehensive, replicable and self-sustaining way. Through two flagship programmes, the AfriConEU Networking Academy will empower and enable African DIHs to best serve their local industries, boost their start-up ecosystems, and empower the youth populations in their communities with the necessary skills to thrive in a digitalised world.

The project includes 11 partners from Europe and Africa: ATBN, BUNI HUB, DPIXEL, ECA, HAPA, INOVA+, ITC, OUTBOX, PBS, STIMMULI, and YMH.

Project duration: 01.02.2021-01.02.2024

Topic: ICT-58-2020: International partnership building between European and African innovation hubs

Introduction

Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH) are support organisations that make businesses more competitive by speeding up the development and uptake of digital innovations. DIHs are one-stop shops that help companies become more competitive concerning their business and production processes, products, or services using digital technologies. DIHs provide access to technical expertise and experimentation so that companies can "test before invest." They also offer innovation services, such as financing advice, training, and skills development needed for a successful digital transformation.

Figure 1: Task of DIHS as defined by the European Commission

The DIH model is entirely in line with the multi-actor approach.

Organisations, which help DIHs (below DIH helpers) can be organisations, networks, initiatives, projects, and more. These organisations help DIHs with:

- Guidelines or programmes for developing DIHs focused on key non-technological issues: ecosystem assessment, business models for DIHs, innovation brokerages, use cases, access to finance;

- Enhancing the collaboration between different stakeholders in the DIH Community with a range of services, information, and tools that help DIHs communicate, align, collaborate and synchronise activities;
- Creating the communities to foster interaction among DIHs, information exchange, and peer-learning.

Existing organisations to strengthen DIH capacities both in Africa and Europe are presented in section

Overview of DIH ecosystem = DIH helpers.

Based on research on the needs of African DIHs, as well as the needs assessment conducted in T2.1 from WP2 and feedback from experts, best practices from existing organisations will be identified.

The aims of this research are to identify:

- How DIHs are trained through DIH establishment, strategy, and business development; service portfolio and development; expansion & networking; sector-specific topic; skills & knowledge creation; communication & awareness;
- What training methods are utilised;
- How knowledge sharing is facilitated;
- What outcomes are achieved;
- How is the measurement of achievement being performed;
- If and which contextual and cultural factors affect DIH's professional development.

For further insights, in-depth interviews with trainers and trainees who participated in these existing programmes were conducted. The results of the survey are presented in chapter *Overview of Capacity Building Programmes for DIHs, both fully operational and those in preparation.*

Approach and methodology

This chapter deals with the approach we used for finding capacity building materials, which will serve DIHs in expanding their knowledge and support them in their capacity building. Steps that were taken:

- Based on previous experience in projects, a first outline of the main steps to establish and operate the hub has been developed to provide a directed overview of materials needed specifically for this purpose;
- Needs related to establishing and operating the DIHs were identified based on the needs assessment report developed in WP2 and interviews with DIHs across Europe and Africa;
- An overview was made of capacity building needs that have already been identified in the project and summarised in 6 categories;
- A web search of available capacity building materials was performed. The aim was to find brief and instructional materials that the DIHs could use. Materials were mapped and collected in a spreadsheet, which is public on the project's webpage.

The list of all the materials themselves is in the chapter *Overview of capacity building*.

Overview of DIH ecosystem = DIH helpers

Each DIH helper is presented in a box with short information about the program and its offered services.

Table 1: DIH services

1	DIH establishment
2	DIH strategy & business development
3	DIH service portfolio & development
4	DIH expansion & networking
5	DIH skills & knowledge creation
6	DIH communication & awareness creation
7	DIH sector-specific topics

In the following tables, the identified DIH helpers are presented.

Table 2: Basic information about DIH Networks

DIH Helper Name	Digital Innovation Hub Networks
Logo	
Web page	https://dihnet.eu/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	The DIHNET.EU project enables the coordination of European, national and regional initiatives directly supporting digital transformation and Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs). The project creates a sustainable pan-European network of networks, with a focus on regional DIHs through the DIHNET.EU Community
Capacity building programmes	DIH establishment DIH expansion & networking

Table 3: Basic information about DIH HELP

DIH Helper Name	DIH HELP
Logo	
Web page	https://dihelp.eu/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	DIHELP stands for "Digital Innovation Hubs Enhanced-Learning Programme". DIHELP aims to develop a coherent, coordinated and sustainable approach to support industries in all EU Member States at a regional level. DIHELP has developed DIH Academy, a mentoring and coaching programme for DIHs to become sustainable. DIHELP has supported 30 DIHs to develop and/or scale up their activities through DIH Academy .
Capacity building programmes offer	DIH strategy & business development DIH skills & knowledge creation

Table 4: Basic information about Smart Agri Hubs

DIH Helper Name	SMART AGRI HUBS
Logo	
Web page	https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	<p>SmartAgriHubs is a consortium of over 164 partners in the European agri-food sector. The project aims to facilitate European agriculture's digitalisation by fostering an agricultural innovation ecosystem dedicated to excellence, sustainability, and success.</p> <p>In the portal, there are open calls, networking, a library, and training (E-learning, on location, and webinar).</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DIH establishment DIH strategy & business development DIH service portfolio & development DIH expansion & networking DIH skills & knowledge creation DIH communication & awareness creation DIH sector-specific topics

Table 5: Basic information about AI DIH network

DIH Helper Name	AI DIH network
Logo	
Web page	https://ai-dih-network.eu/index.html
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	AI DIH network is a framework for continuous collaboration and networking between DIHs focusing on Artificial Intelligence (AI). The aim is to help DIHs unlock their collaborative and networking potential via mentoring, coaching and co-creation activities. Based on evidence resulting from demonstration activities, the project has developed a blueprint for cross-border collaboration as well as supporting measures and policy recommendations or enhancing collaboration and networking potential. Training materials are available in the form of webinars, workshops, training packages, and coaching and mentoring programmes.
Capacity building programmes offer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DIH strategy & business development DIH expansion & networking DIH skills & knowledge creation DIH sector-specific topic

Table 6: Basic information about ICT Innovation for Manufacturing SMEs

DIH Helper Name	ICT Innovation for Manufacturing SMEs (I4MS)
Logo	
Web page	https://i4ms.eu/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	I4MS is one of the EC's key initiatives to shape the pan-European network of Digital Innovation Hubs. I4MS support manufacturing SMEs and mid-caps in the widespread use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in their business operations. Training is currently available 129 trainings on different topics.
Capacity building programmes offer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DIH strategy & business development DIH service portfolio & development DIH expansion & networking DIH skills & knowledge creation DIH sector-specific topics

Table 7: Basic information about The Smart Anything Everywhere

DIH Helper Name	The Smart Anything Everywhere (SAE)
Logo	
Web page	https://smartanythingeverywhere.eu/about/
Type of organisation	Initiative
Short description	The SAE Initiative aligns different projects (Innovation Actions) in various technology areas such as cyber-physical and embedded systems, customized low energy computing powering cyber-physical systems and the internet of things, flexible and wearable electronics/organic large area electronics, and widening digital innovation hubs. In the section Success story , good practices are presented in the different technology areas. In the section Services, are training on different topics.
Capacity building programmes offer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DIH establishment DIH strategy & business development DIH service portfolio & development DIH expansion & networking DIH skills & knowledge creation DIH communication & awareness creation DIH sector-specific topics

Table 8: Basic information about DigiFed

DIH Helper Name	DigiFed
Logo	
Web page	https://digifed.org/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	DigiFed implements a business plan for the sustainability of a federation of DIHs while providing a significant support mechanism for individuals and groups of SMEs to foster digital technologies in their product and service offerings. In the section Explore , several webinars and bootcamps on different topics of digitalisation are presented, (as cybersecurity, IoT-AI, etc.).
Capacity building programmes offer	DIH sector-specific topics

Table 9: Basic information about HUBCAP

DIH Helper Name	HUBCAP
Logo	
Web page	https://www.hubcap.eu/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	HUBCAP is a one-stop-shop for embracing digital innovation using model-based design technology for Cyber-Physical Systems, getting the tools and resources you need to scale ideas and grow your business. In their service section, partners offer various services: knowledge, technology services, fast prototyping and validation, ecosystem building, access to market and funding.
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH service portfolio & development</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p> <p>DIH sector-specific topics</p>

Table 10: Basic information about Digital for Development (D4D) Hub

DIH Helper Name	Digital for Development (D4D) Hub
Logo	
Web page	https://d4dlaunch.eu/
Type of organisation	Network
Short description	<p>D4D Hub is a new international partnership on digital transformation. It is a key tool for putting a “Team Europe” in action with unprecedented levels of coordination, advancing multi-stakeholder dialogue to leverage expertise and resources, and sharing best practices.</p> <p>AU-EU D4D provides demand-driven technical support to national stakeholders, disseminates best practices, and hosts digital policy dialogues between inter-African and African-EU multi-stakeholders partnerships.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	DIH expansion & networking

Table 11: Basic information about ITU-D Digital Innovation Ecosystems

DIH Helper Name	ITU-D Digital Innovation Ecosystems
Logo	
Web page	https://www.itu.int/itu-d/sites/innovation/
Type of organisation	Network
Short description	ITU-D Digital Innovation Ecosystems is the thematic priority to empower members to unlock their digital potential, build their capabilities in innovation and entrepreneurship, and accelerate their ecosystems impact on cross-cutting sectors for an inclusive society. Its resources are restricted to member state actors and those they invite.
Capacity building programmes offer	DIH skills & networking

Table 12: Basic information about EIT Digital

DIH Helper Name	EIT Digital
Logo	
Web page	https://www.eitdigital.eu/
Type of organisation	Organisation
Short description	EIT Digital embodies the future of innovation by mobilising a pan-European, multi-stakeholder open-innovation ecosystem of top European corporations, SMEs, start-ups, universities, and other actors, which addresses the technology, talent, skills, business, and capital needs of digital entrepreneurship.
Capacity building programmes offer	DIH expansion & networking DIH sector-specific topics

Table 13: Basic information about AfriLabs

DIH Helper Name	AfriLabs
Logo	
Web page	https://www.afrilabs.com/
Type of organisation	Network
Short description	<p>AfriLabs is a network and organisation of 268 innovation centres across 49 African countries. It supports hubs to raise successful entrepreneurs that will create jobs and develop innovative solutions to African problems. AfriLabs objectives are to encourage technology, innovation, and entrepreneurship in all forms; to promote the creation of African-made technology; to promote open collaboration, technical innovations and support for the technological community at large; and to provide commitment to capacity building, mentorship, networking and forming bonds.</p> <p>Based on research on African hub needs, capacity gaps and best practices, AfriLabs conduct AfriLabs Capacity Building Programme (ACBP) for hubs, emphasising business development and investment management.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH strategy & business development</p> <p>DIH expansion & networking</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p>

Table 14: Basic information about Boosting digital innovation

DIH Helper Name	Boosting digital innovation (BOWI)
Logo	
Web page	https://bowi-network.eu/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	<p>BOWI project connects digital innovation hubs and SMEs in the discovery of advanced digital solutions. It aims to build a DIH network based on experience and practice sharing. The network supports companies in bringing their most innovative projects to life, aids investors in discovering the leaders of the digital revolution, and helps development agencies understand industry needs. BOWI explores the best solutions for DIH cooperation in the form of technology transfer experiments. They provide open calls for mature DIHs who will benefit from collaboration with developing DIHs, tech transfer experiments, new collaboration and networking. Open calls for developing DIHs provide a 21-month long mentoring and support programme.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH strategy & business development</p> <p>DIH expansion & networking</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p>

Table 15: Basic information about DIH-World

DIH Helper Name	DIH-World
Logo	
Web page	https://dihworld.eu/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	<p>DIH-World aims to harmonise and widen the landscape of European DIHs across all of Europe to address the "digital innovation hubs divide". It aims to accelerate the uptake of advanced digital technologies by European manufacturing SMEs in all sectors and strengthens the capacities of regional DIHs.</p> <p>DIH-World supports DIHs with training and mentoring and will provide them access to a wide range of good practices. The objectives of the DIH-World Academy are to develop and support DIHs to help them define a sustainable business model, support DIH collaboration, and help them develop or fine-tune their value propositions. Services: training camps, regional dissemination workshops, tailored training, toolbox.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH strategy & business development</p> <p>DIH expansion & networking</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p>

Table 16: Basic information about Open Data Incubator Europe

DIH Helper Name	ODINE (Open Data Incubator Europe)
Logo	
Web page	https://opendataincubator.eu/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	<p>The Open Data Incubator for Europe (ODINE) is a 6-month incubator for open data entrepreneurs across Europe. ODINE aims to support the next generation of digital businesses and support them to fast-track the development of their products.</p> <p>On the subpage, Resources are different available resources on topics: Business strategy, data, funding, marketing, ODINE SMEs, Offers. Reports, tech tools, Training & webinars, videos.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH strategy & business development</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p> <p>DIH communication & awareness creation</p>

Table 17: Basic information about European Network for Pilot Production Facilities and Innovation Hubs

DIH Helper Name	European Network for Pilot Production Facilities and Innovation Hubs (EPPN)
Logo	
Web page	https://www.eppnetwork.com/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	<p>EPP's overall goal is to boost the European competitiveness through the exploitation of the existing European pilot line production facilities in the area of nanotechnology and advanced material technologies by creating a network of fully connected and collaborating pilot lines and boosting the effectiveness and the efficiency of pilot line facilities and by creating a digital ecosystem acting as an interactive marketplace for professional members.</p> <p>The project aims at leveraging technological research into a product demonstration and further contributing to an enhanced innovation ecosystem and attractive business environment by creating a sustainable ecosystem involving all the stakeholders capable of promoting collaboration along the value chain, developing supporting tools for pilot plants and potential users, promoting the creation of IH, catalysing and fostering the sustainable business development of the EPPN.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH service portfolio & development</p> <p>DIH expansion & networking</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p> <p>DIH sector-specific topics</p>

Table 18: Basic information about European cluster collaboration platform

DIH Helper Name	European cluster collaboration platform
Logo	
Web page	https://clustercollaboration.eu/
Type of organisation	Initiative
Short description	<p>The European cluster collaboration platform is the European online hub for industry clusters to strengthen the European economy through collaboration. The services support short-term exchanges to better connect Europe's industrial clusters and their ecosystems, provide an overview of relevant funding and tenders, it also organises and shares events related to cluster development and has a knowledge sharing forum for its registered members.</p> <p>Registered members have access to a knowledge sharing forum. The mapping tool currently contains information from the profiles of cluster actors registered on the ECCP. On the subpage Publication, there is unlimited access to the latest reports and studies for insight and recommendations from helpful cluster practitioners and latest trends, policy measures and publications from experts within the ECCP community.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH strategy & business development</p> <p>DIH expansion & networking</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p>

Table 19: Basic information about The European Resource Efficiency Knowledge Centre

DIH Helper Name	The European Resource Efficiency Knowledge Centre
Logo	
Web page	https://resourceefficient.eu/en/
Type of organisation	Initiative
Short description	<p>The European Resource Efficiency Knowledge Centre (EREK) helps European companies, especially SMEs, save resources and engage in circular economy and industrial symbiosis. EREK provides tools, information and business opportunities demonstrating new and better ways to be resource efficient and benefit from circular economy business models, which turn waste into assets. Concrete activities include an online platform, news, trends and information on support programmes, a database, and capacity-building and training workshops.</p> <p>To help companies test their performance in resource efficiency, they have developed a Self-Assessment Tool (SAT). Companies received a tailored report grouping together all gathered information and recommendations on becoming more resource-efficient for 11 sectors: office, timber and woodworking, waste collection services, food processing, manufacturing and machinery and equipment, hotels and restaurants, metal and plastics processing, wholesale and retail, textile and clothing, chemicals and process, constructions.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH strategy & business development</p> <p>DIH service portfolio & development</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p> <p>DIH sector-specific topics</p>

Table 20: Basic information about The Africa-Europe Innovation Partnership

DIH Helper Name	The Africa-Europe Innovation Partnership
Logo	
Web page	https://africaeurope-innovationpartnership.net/about
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	<p>The Africa-Europe Innovation Partnership aims to support and connect innovation and technology incubators and accelerators in tapping into new markets, find trusted partners across the Mediterranean as well as build new perspectives, knowledge, and networks. The AEIP seeks to build mutually beneficial partnerships and networks between the two continents by addressing both issues faced by entrepreneurs pursuing growth internationally and challenges in harnessing funding opportunities.</p> <p>The AEIP develops training modules for start-ups, entrepreneurs, and intermediary organisations, seeking synergies with existing training and adapting training materials to local needs and style. Generic training modules cover EU funding opportunities, whereas Technology modules will focus on intercontinental collaboration in innovation projects. On the subpage Resources, more than 50 useful resources are available on topics such as European funding opportunities, tech-hub management and business models, innovative approaches to start-up support and technology transfer.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH strategy & business development</p> <p>DIH service portfolio & development</p> <p>DIH expansion & networking</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p>

Table 21: Basic information about Ghana Hubs Network

DIH Helper Name	Ghana Hubs Network
Logo	
Web page	https://www.ghanahubsnetwork.com/
Type of organisation	Network
Short description	<p>Ghana Hubs network provides supportive services to their stakeholder community of entrepreneurs, innovation hubs, NGOs, and governments. They facilitate access to three critical resources: training, funding and networking. On behalf of their network members and the entire entrepreneurial ecosystem, they advocate policies with governmental bodies.</p> <p>A collection of online workshops helps hub managers and staff acquire additional knowledge and connections to support entrepreneurship. The Series helps strengthen their organisation so that they can sustainably achieve their goals and mission. The workshops are available after registration.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH expansion & networking</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p> <p>DIH communication & awareness creation</p>

Table 22: Basic information about Innovation Support Network - Hubs

DIH Helper Name	Innovation Support Network – Hubs (ISN-HUBS)
Logo	
Web page	https://www.isnhubs.org.ng/about
Type of organisation	Network
Short description	<p>ISN-HUBS represents an organised community of Hubs in Nigeria to promote collaboration amongst hubs, entrepreneurship, and innovation across Nigeria. They provide capacity development programs that enable hub operators to enhance their entrepreneurship support services. They set standards through facilitating the identification, exchange and use of commercial best practices for workspaces, incubators and accelerators. They also engage with policymakers on the role of hubs in support of job-creating social and commercial ventures in the Nigerian economy.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH strategy & business development</p> <p>DIH service portfolio & development</p> <p>DIH expansion & networking</p>

Table 23: Basic information about The Association of Startup and SMEs Enablers of Kenya

DIH Helper Name	The Association of Startup and SMEs Enablers of Kenya (ASSEK)
Logo	<p>The logo for ASSEK features a stylized red and black graphic above the word "assek" in a bold, black, lowercase sans-serif font.</p>
Web page	https://www.isnhubs.org.ng/about
Type of organisation	Network
Short description	<p>ASSEK is an association that brings together and represents organisations' interests supporting the development and growth of start-ups and SMEs in Kenya. ASSEK enhanced collaboration between members (sharing information, knowledge and best practices), capacity building, policy, empowerment through collaborations and partnership and internationalisation.</p> <p>They provide capacity development programs and professional development. They facilitate peer-to-peer learning workshops and round tables, organise knowledge exchange programs and co-create a collective code of conduct and standards.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH strategy & business development</p> <p>DIH expansion & networking</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p>

Table 24: Basic information about Funding Box

DIH Helper Name	Funding Box
Logo	
Web page	https://fundingbox.com/
Type of organisation	Network
Short description	Funding box champions entrepreneurs and innovators eager to ignite their growth to rewrite their future through easy-to-apply funding opportunities and tailor-made acceleration programmes. They matchmake global brands and investors with promising start-ups to put on track profitable collaborations that will accelerate their innovation processes. They provide funding information, connections to different communities, scale-up innovation processes, and knowledge sharing.
Capacity building programmes offer	DIH service portfolio & development DIH expansion & networking

Table 25: Basic information about I4Trust

DIH Helper Name	I4Trust
Logo	
Web page	https://i4trust.org/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	<p>I4Trust builds a sustainable ecosystem where companies can create innovative services by breaking "data silos" by sharing, re-using, and trading data assets, developing innovative services based on data sharing and creating new data-driven business models. They contribute to the digital transformation of industrial value chains across multiple domains.</p> <p>They provide different types of programmes in the field of data spaces, like the Train the Trainers program for DIHs. In the Resources section, some material is available on the topic of data sharing.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH service portfolio & development</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p> <p>DIH sector-specific topics</p>

Table 26: Basic information about Impact Ed Tech

DIH Helper Name	Impact Ed Tech
Logo	
Web page	https://impactedtech.eu/impact-edtech/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	<p>The European Incubator-Accelerator helps EdTech start-ups and SMEs turn ideas into market-ready products, break the barriers to education, and enhance learning experiences in a new era of human-centred digital education. IMPACT EdTech provides expert knowledge, educational resources, and data.</p> <p>Education and digital learning through a hybrid incubator-accelerator. Inclusive education, targeting specific underserved or vulnerable groups, personalised learning with a focus on supporting new, research-based pedagogical approaches for in-classroom education and encouraging life-long learning. Skill development focuses on the development of STEM, critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication. 3 open calls.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH service portfolio & development</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p> <p>DIH sector-specific topics</p>

Table 27: Basic information about The European Coordination Hub for Open Robotics Development

DIH Helper Name	The European Coordination Hub for Open Robotics Development (ECHORD++)
Logo	
Web page	http://echord.eu/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	The original strategic mission of ECHORD was to enable researchers to use industrial-level equipment for know-how transfer experiments, encourage researchers and manufacturers to identify and work together on emerging technology scenarios through establishing a structured dialogue between all players, extract, consolidate and broadcast the actual progress achieved in the experiments to the robotics community. They provide experiments and good practices from different sectors in the field of robotics.
Capacity building programmes offer	DIH service portfolio & development DIH expansion & networking DIH sector-specific topics

Table 28: Basic information about Smart Factories in new EU Member States

DIH Helper Name	Smart Factories in new EU Member States
Logo	
Web page	https://smartfactories.eu/
Type of organisation	Project
Short description	<p>The project "Smart Factories in new EU Member States" aims at building a DIHs network in Europe, where companies could have access to expertise, development and testing facilities of digital technologies, as well as access to finance and innovation services. 34 DIH applicants have been selected to take part in the Training & Mentoring programme.</p> <p>The training & mentoring programme includes different types of activities such as developing a specific business plan, training and coaching, provision of manuals and relevant documentation, the establishment of potential funding schemes, and organisation of regional workshops. On the subpage, Library, some material from this trainings is available.</p>
Capacity building programmes offer	<p>DIH establishment</p> <p>DIH strategy & business development</p> <p>DIH skills & knowledge creation</p>

Overview of Capacity Building Programmes for DIHS, both fully operational and those in preparation

Five supporting guiding principles for capacity building are:

- Ease of access;
- Goal setting;
- Proactivity;
- Collaboration (peer-to-peer feedback);
- Engagement mechanisms.

The selection of materials was based on the identified needs in the AfriConEU community and whether, following our guiding principles, an open-access webinar or template is available on the topics. Multiple projects addressed some topics. Here, the decision on which training to include in the AfriConEU portal has been based on the team's judgment and the relevance of the training.

This overview is actually a snapshot of a live document that will continuously be updated by the team as new needs in the community are identified.

The mapped materials will support new DIHs in setting up their organisation and already operating DIHs in optimising their operations and services. Some of the trainings identified are of importance in both of these stages.

Table 29: List of capacity building programmes for DIHs

#	Title	Tool	Who?	Web page	Payable /Free	Duration	Duration Format	Short description	Theme
1	Ecosystem Building & the role of DIHs	Webinar	I4trust	https://youtu.be/ObDu1StYDA	free	02:45	hh:mm	The first part of the session elaborates on the approach adopted towards building the i4Trust Community and the second elaborates on the OnBoarding; the role of DIHs.	DIH ecosystem
2	Innovation ecosystems: Cooperation between Africa and Europe	Webinar	DIHNET.EU	https://spaces.fundingbox.com/spaces/dihnet-eu-community-innovation-ecosystems-cooperation-between-africa-and-europe/5f7de20af9a7a75c28f3602c	free	02:01	hh:mm	Innovation ecosystem in Europe and Africa and main initiatives there, best practices.	DIH ecosystem
3	DIH Ecosystem Building Event	Online Event	SAE	https://youtu.be/7KoUSgatUby (Part 1) and https://youtu.be/H9sWbRVfRAk (Part 2)	free	04:00	hh:mm	Learn how regional DIHs can help your company to be more competitive using digital technologies.	DIH ecosystem
4	Best practice webinar: “Engaging relevant	Webinar	DIHELP	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wP-fc5dCuqY	free	00:59	hh:mm	The webinar is focused on how to engage regional SMEs in DIH activities.	DIH ecosystem

	stakeholders in your digital ecosystem”								
5	Collaboration in the (E)DIH ecosystem	PPT for Webinar	DIHNET.EU	https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/library/reports-resources/Presentations/2020-1022-DIHNET-SmartAgrihubs-presentation-collaboration-in-the-EU-ecosystem-1603379566.pdf	free	33	PPT	Collaboration, EU networks, and funding.	DIH ecosystem
6	Collaboration in the (E)DIH ecosystem	PPT for Webinar	DIHNET.EU	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LjvYsl3Gv_E	free	00:58	hh:mm	Collaboration, EU networks, and funding.	DIH ecosystem
7	Ecosystem Landscaping	Worksheet	Smart Factories in new member states	https://smartfactories.eu/uploads/7b848e7ce7c6a2a9222acbfa4a18577a3fcd7019.xlsx	free	1	worksheet	This worksheet is provided as an example to support you in mapping the innovation ecosystem of your Digital Innovation HUB (DIH).	DIH ecosystem
8	Steps towards creating a DIH	PPT for Webinar	DIHNET.EU	https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/library/reports-resources/Presentations/20	free	35	PPT	Webinar on what a Digital Innovation Hub is and what are the steps to develop it.	DIH establishment

				20-0131-SAH-how-to-develop-a-DIH_M-Butter-1580481436.pdf					
9	Steps towards creating a DIH	Webinar	DIHNET.EU	https://youtu.be/KglUBKiqv_uE	free	01:03	hh:mm	Webinar on what a Digital Innovation Hub is and what are the steps to develop it.	DIH establishment
10	Cooperation between Start-Ups and DIHs	Webinar	DIHNET.EU	https://spaces.fundingbox.com/spaces/dihnet-eu-digital-innovation-hubs-community-dihnet-eu-news/5ecfa602d155675821fa0bbf	free	01:30	hh:mm	Webinar to increase cooperation between Start-ups and DIHs.	DIH expansion & networking
11	Post-project sustainability of EU networks	Webinar	DIHNET.EU	https://spaces.fundingbox.com/spaces/dihnet-eu-digital-innovation-hubs-community-dihnet-eu-news/5f1fe2c14fb658397263dfb3	free	01:06	hh:mm	The webinar focuses on how to improve the sustainability of pan-EU networks and aims to provide insights on how to strategically and operationally address post-project sustainability. 3 aspects: network services, revenue models to get financial sustainability, branding and communication.	DIH expansion & networking
12	Blueprint for cross-border	Document	AI DIH Network	https://www.ai-dih-network.eu/media_and_training.html	free	40	Pages	The document provides an overview of what it means to be an AI DIH, how to get ready for cross-border collaboration and how to evaluate	DIH expansion & networking

	collaboration among DIHs							your readiness to cooperate. The blueprint also presents some of the key outcomes of the project.	
13	Digital Innovation Hubs in Europe	Interactive maps	Europe Commission	https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/digital-innovation-hubs-tool	free	1	list	The list of all DIHs in EU, searchable by country, evolutionary stages, technologies, provided services, focus on TRL and sectors.	DIH expansion & networking
14	I4MS Skills Catalogue	Trainings	I4MS	https://trainings.i4ms.eu/	free	-	-	Collection of more than 100 trainings throughout Europe.	DIH sector-specific topics
15	EREK knowledge base of resource efficiency	Knowledge Base	EREK	https://www.resourceefficiency.eu/en/database	free	619	Lessons	Measures, technologies and good practices on resource efficiency.	DIH sector-specific topics
16	SAH Capacity Building training: SmartAgriHubs DIH Innovation Services	Webinar	Smart Agri Hubs	https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/portal/trainings?search=on%20Services%20Maturity%20model&id=5854	free	01:00	hh:mm	SAH Innovation Services Maturity Model – a practical tool to help DIHs assess the state of development of their services. SmartAgriHubs has developed an Innovation Services Maturity Model, which allows you DIH affiliates to assess the state of development of the technology, business, and ecosystem services they provide	DIH service portfolio & development

	Maturity model							to partners in their ecosystems. This helps them to identify strengths and weaknesses and helps to identify concrete steps to go to the next levels.	
17	DIHs serving the public sector: support services to foster the uptake of new technologies	PPT for Webinar	DIH WORLD	https://dihworld.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Webinar-20-July_PwC_v1.0-1.pdf	free	62	PPT	This webinar focuses on DIHs serving the public sector in order to foster the uptake of innovative technologies, a relevant topic also within the context of the Digital Europe Programme.	DIH service portfolio & development
18	Skills and capacities for DIH	Webinar	Smart Agri Hubs	https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/portal/trainings?id=1925	free	01:00	hh:mm	Developing skills and offering trainings is essential to allow farmers and citizens to make the best of the digital opportunities. But what skills exactly are needed? And how can DIHs address different groups of stakeholders? What skills do the hubs need to develop themselves? What instruments and training approaches can be used by hubs?	DIH skills & knowledge creation

19	i4Trust Training	Webinar	I4trust	https://i4trust.org/training/	free	8	Sessions	These training sessions provide the necessary i4Trust know-how to support experiments and their transfer to the market. Discover all the potential of data sharing enabling cross/domain data value chains.	DIH skills & knowledge creation
20	Turning organizations into Smart Organizations	Webinar	FIWARE	https://youtu.be/XsoXchKiKB4	free	01:00	hh:mm	The webinar covers the "system of systems" approach and FIWARE transformation journey, also with the help of success stories.	DIH skills & knowledge creation
21	FIWARE Vision and Value Proposition for a Smart Future	Webinar	FIWARE	https://youtu.be/7ZMUYEWD1gw	free	00:50	hh:mm	A broad overview of the value proposition of FIWARE and its position in a Smart Digital Future.	DIH skills & knowledge creation
22	Value creation Through Innovation Specialization	Online Course	EIT Digital	https://www.coursera.org/specializations/value-creation-innovation	free	156:00	hh:mm	Capture the value of technology. Understand, predict and leverage on technology-driven transformations. (4h/week for 9 months)	DIH skills & knowledge creation
23	Open data modules	E-Modules	Odine	https://data.europa.eu/elementary/en/#/id/co-01	free	16	Lessons	This programme has been designed to enable participants to discover what open data is and how it is changing the lives of everyone on our planet.	DIH skills & knowledge creation

24	Open data handbook	Handbook	Odine	http://opendatahandbook.org/guide/en/	free	-	hh:mm	This handbook discusses the legal, social and technical aspects of open data. It can be used by anyone but is specially designed for those seeking to open up data. It discusses the why, what and how of open data – why to go open, what open is, and the how to ‘open’ data.	DIH skills & knowledge creation
25	Business Models and Strategy for DIHs	Module	Smart Agri Hubs	https://smartagrihubs.curator3.com/courses/dih-exchange/home#level/232328	free	02:30	hh:mm	The objective of this module is to understand the multi-sidedness and the indirectness of the DIH business model, its service portfolio, as well as being able to configure it to a DIH according to the overall strategic vision of the DIH. Overall, this module aims to support DIHs in setting up their strategy as well as designing their business model.	DIH strategy & business development
26	Financing of DIHs	Module	Smart Agri Hubs	https://smartagrihubs.curator3.com/courses/dih-exchange/home#level/236613	free	01:14	hh:mm	This module aims to provide DIHs with some high-level information on how DIHs themselves, as an initiative, can be financed and the elements they should consider. The module aims to support the DIHs in developing their financing by providing them with: a structure of how DIHs can look at their financing, good	DIH strategy & business development

								practices, tips on pitching and template to help DIHs map their services/funding matrix.	
27	Access to finance	Webinar	I4MS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=igHeNZQGsmw	free	01:30	hh:mm	The webinar provides basic information about access to finance.	DIH strategy & business development
28	Building a Business plan	Webinar	I4MS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ngvdPZ1Wsuk	free	00:53	hh:mm	Create an overview of the core elements of a business plan for an innovation hub, create practical insights on how to develop these different elements to provide a holistic overview of a business plan when starting the development of a hub, will support a more focused and efficient hub development process.	DIH strategy & business development
29	Business Models	Webinar	I4MS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9ZI_56w9zJI	free	01:00	hh:mm	Increase the knowledge base and structure of thinking about business models and services for infrastructures, initiate the thinking about making money for hub consortia and the services they can provide. To focus DIHs on concrete activities and shifting the thinking of the consortia from the technological focus towards making money.	DIH strategy & business development

30	Ecosystem Assessment	Webinar	I4MS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9ZI_56w9zJI	free	01:08	hh:mm	This webinar provide basic information about ecosystem assesment and five steps to assess it.	DIH strategy & business development
31	Brokerage	Webinar	I4MS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rUGFC7Vwk2w	free	01:40	hh:mm	This webinar provide basic information about brokerage and brokerage system provided by I4MS.	DIH strategy & business development
32	Funding and financing opportunities for DIHs	Webinar	AI DIH Network	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wrKLA16TE6o	free	01:16	hh:mm	Latest development regarding the Digital Europe Programme, especially the financial instruments	DIH strategy & business development
33	How to make investors fall in love with your company	Webinar	SAE	https://smartanythingeverywhere.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/SAE-workshop-How-to-make-investors-falling-in-love-with-your-company.mp4	free	00:56	hh:mm	The webinar covers the topic of private financing, tips, mistakes to avoid, expected content and process to raise private financing.	DIH strategy & business development
34	DIH Sharing Experiences - Podcast Episode 2:	Webinar	DIHNET.EU	https://spaces.fundingbox.com/spaces/dihnet-eu-digital-innovation-hubs-community-dihnet-eu-	free	00:41	hh:mm	Two hubs from Spain and from Slovenia talking about public funding.	DIH strategy & business development

	"How to attract public funding for DIHs"			news/5e1ca94052317832f8591c3f					
35	Digitising Europe's industry together	Webinar	DigiFed	https://digifed.org/2020/03/10/webinar-digitising-europes-industry-together/	free	01:30	hh:mm	Discover the cascade funding opportunity by DigiFed, the innovation action supported by the Horizon 2020 programme driving the digital revolution across European SMEs.	DIH strategy & business development
36	Innovation & Entrepreneurs hip - From Basics to Open Innovation	Online Course	EIT Digital	https://www.coursera.org/learn/open-innovation-entrepreneurship	free	16:00	hh:mm	This Innovation and Entrepreneurship course focuses on the interconnection between entrepreneurial thinking and innovation.	DIH strategy & business development
37	Innovation & Entrepreneurs hip - From Design Thinking to Funding	Online Course	EIT Digital	https://www.coursera.org/learn/design-thinking-entrepreneurship	free	12:00	hh:mm	From Design Thinking to Funding, the following areas are included: design thinking; innovation cycle process; business modelling; and funding.	DIH strategy & business development

38	Data Science for Business Innovation	Online Course	EIT Digital	https://www.coursera.org/learn/data-science-for-business-innovation	free	07:00	hh:mm	The course is a compendium of the must-have expertise in data science for executive and middle-management to foster data-driven innovation. It consists of introductory lectures spanning big data, machine learning, data valorization and communication. Topics cover the essential concepts and intuitions on data needs, data analysis, machine learning methods, respective pros and cons, and practical applicability issues.	DIH strategy & business development
39	Sustainable Digital Innovation	Online Course	EIT Digital	https://www.coursera.org/learn/sustainable-digital-innovation	free	13:00	hh:mm	Sustainable Digital Innovation will provide you with - an understanding of the sustainable contextual framework - the methods and tools for your business to address sustainable challenges of different means - an overview on how digital technologies can help you manage and innovate your role in your business ecosystem and support sustainable development in business and society - insights into the existing and emerging cases of digitally enabled sustainable solutions as these solutions are of value to industries on various markets.	DIH strategy & business development

40	Impact from Digital Transformation: Full course	Online Course	EIT Digital	https://www.coursera.org/learn/digital-transformation-impact	free	07:00	hh:mm	This course is about what you can do when everything around you seems to be moving due to digital change. It is about how to handle the disruptive process that tends to unfold in the industry nowadays due to digitalisation. The way to handle this is what is here referred to as "Digital Transformation" and at the core of it, it is about understanding how the new business landscape is evolving and heading for a new position in that landscape. It is about corporate strategy.	DIH strategy & business development
41	Business Implications of AI: Full course	Online Course	EIT Digital	https://www.coursera.org/learn/business-implications-ai	free	06:00	hh:mm	In this course, you will learn what Artificial Intelligence is, from a leaders point of view. How shall we, as leaders, understand it from a corporate strategy point of view? What is it and how can it be used? What are the crucial strategic decisions we have to make, and how to make them? What consequences can we expect if we decide on doing AI-projects and what kind of competences do we need? Where shall we start, and what could be a good second	DIH strategy & business development

								as well as a third step? What implications for the organization can we expect?	
42	Marketing Strategy for Entrepreneurs	Online Course	EIT Digital	https://www.coursera.org/learn/marketing-strategy-entrepreneurs	free	13:00	hh:mm	this course will prepare you for some of the most common marketing and sales efforts needed for technology based companies.	DIH strategy & business development
43	Capstone Value Creation through Innovation	Online Course	EIT Digital	https://www.coursera.org/learn/capstone-value-creation-innovation	free	68:00	hh:mm	The course covers technology bases innovation and transformation and how to spot and capitalize on emerging opportunities.	DIH strategy & business development
44	How to Start a Startup	Trainings	Odine	http://startupclass.samaltman.com/	free	20	Lectures	Everything they know about how to start a startup, for free, from some of the world experts.	DIH strategy & business development
45	EOCIC: The Smart Guide to entrepreneurship support through clusters	Smart guide	ECCP	https://clustercollaboration.eu/sites/default/files/eu_initiatives/eocic_smart_guide_to_entrepreneurship.pdf	free	78	Pages	The purpose of this Smart Guide is to provide guidance to cluster policymakers and cluster managers in designing and implementing programmes that accelerate the creation of start-ups, spin-offs and scale-ups in emerging industries and in specific value chains. By focusing on innovative entrepreneurship, this	DIH strategy & business development

								guide offers practical help on how clusters can mobilise resources to effectively support entrepreneurship throughout the entire entrepreneurial life cycle.	
46	The Smart Guide for European Strategic Cluster Partnerships (ESCP)	Smart guide	ECCP	https://clustercollaboration.eu/sites/default/files/news_attachment/smart_guide_for_european_strategic_cluster_partnerships.pdf	free	103	Pages	The Smart Guide for European Strategic Cluster Partnerships (ESCP) aims to provide guidance to ESCP on how to develop a successful partnership strategy and on possible actions to achieve joint projects and investments. For that purpose, the Smart Guide presents an overview of the main challenges and specific barriers faced by ESCP, mainly related to the establishment and improvement of partnerships as well as to fostering innovation, cooperation and internationalisation. Considering those challenges, the Smart Guide also provides a set of recommended actions to establish sustainable partnership strategies and joint activities, as well as a sample of related good practices.	DIH strategy & business development

47	The Smart Guide to Cluster Policy	Smart guide	ECCP	https://clustercollaboration.eu/sites/default/files/news_attachment/smart_guide_to_cluster_policy.pdf	free	60	Pages	The Smart Guide to Cluster Policy is a new tool for policy-makers and practitioners to support industrial modernisation, SME growth and smart specialisation.	DIH strategy & business development
48	Strategy Development for DIHs	PPT for Webinar	Smart Agri Hubs	https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/library/reports-resources/Presentations/SAH_Strategy_Stavros_V2-1592567947.pdf	free	21	PPT	Strategy development process.	DIH strategy & business development
49	Marketing Plan Template	Worksheet	Smart Factories in new member states	https://smartfactories.eu/uploads/66429b194095aa0a6ec53227bbc5d7cced47af5f.docx	free	1	worksheet	A marketing plan is your roadmap for finding and keeping customers. By planning your marketing step by step, you give your company the best chance of success in today's competitive marketplace.	DIH strategy & business development
50	Governance for Digital Innovation Hubs	Webinar	Smart Agri Hubs	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=00W6ag-S7eQ	free	00:44	hh:mm	The webinar aims to help DIHs in the agri-food sector to identify the key elements they need to consider when setting up their operations and governance structure.	DIH strategy & business development

CONCLUSION

The mapped materials (capacity building programmes) will support new DIHs in setting up their organisation and already operating DIHs in optimising their operations and services. DIHs can find the most valuable information at DIHs helpers. The selection of materials was based on the identified needs in the AfriConEU community. This overview is actually a snapshot of a live document that will continuously be updated by the team as new needs in the community are identified and new trainings emerge. Capacity building is essential for all organizations, because it is the process of developing and organization's strength and sustainability.